

Satellite reaction wheels fault detection based on normalized conformal prediction intervals over symbolic regression

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Abstract. Anomaly detection is a critical component in the monitoring of industrial processes. This work focuses on detecting friction anomalies in satellite reaction wheels (RAW) using a Conformal Anomaly Detection (CAD) framework. Our approach is based on Normalized Inductive Conformal Prediction (NICP), combined with Symbolic Regression (SR) and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) models. RAW friction and its expected nominal behavior are used as a baseline for identifying deviations across 12 distinct anomaly types. To support real-time monitoring, we implement an alarm-based detection system that leverages a sliding window technique for processing streaming data. Our method addresses and resolves certain limitations of CAD in outlier detection by focusing the evaluation windows on the anomalies. Time dependence is incorporated through friction step trend information, which enhances detection performance. This approach also highlights emerging challenges in anomaly detection, where explainability and trustworthiness are essential for practical deployment.

Keywords: Anomaly detection, Conformal Prediction, Symbolic Regression, Normalized Conformal Prediction, Satellite.

1 Introduction

Anomaly detection plays a crucial role across a wide range of industrial and data-driven processes. It tackles the fundamental challenge of distinguishing between *normal* and *abnormal* behavior—a problem that has been approached using a vast array of techniques. Among these, machine learning has been extensively explored, employing diverse algorithms to model and detect deviations. Such

anomalies typically manifest as deviations from established patterns of expected behavior [1].

The problem has been addressed by leveraging the capabilities of Machine learning algorithms like SVM [2], Random Forest [3] , and neural networks [4] to effectively detect anomalies in critical fields such as medicine [5] cybersecurity [6], and robotics [7]. These methods rely on comparing predictions against actual values to fine-tune anomaly detection, often without considering the statistical significance of the prediction.

Conformal Prediction, a concept rooted in machine learning and statistics for over two decades, is pivotal in constructing prediction intervals with guaranteed statistical confidence, independent of data distribution. Developed by Vladimir Vovk, Alex Gammerman, and Glenn Shafer in the early 2000s, its foundations draw from algorithmic randomness and game-theoretic probability, expanding upon their seminal work in "Algorithmic Learning in a Random World" (2005) [8].

While machine learning algorithms predictions are typically evaluated on metrics like accuracy, MSE, and R^2 , the standout feature of conformal prediction lies in its provision of reliable confidence metrics for predictions, making it indispensable in critical applications that require AI trustworthiness such as medicine, finance, and autonomous systems.

In the case of anomaly classification, when working with a specified confidence level, conformal predictors produce a set of predictions that is expected to include the true label (value) with at least the probability set in the confidence level. In classification scenarios, conformal predictors can also indicate the confidence level for the most likely single label, effectively providing a prediction set of size one. The key assumption here is that both the new sample and the training set samples are independently drawn from the same underlying distribution [9].

In this paper we propose a method that uses NICP for regression as an anomaly detector in satellite reaction wheels. In the case of regression, given a confidence level, when *normal* data is fed into conformal predictors, it outputs upper and lower intervals where the prediction should be located with a probability given by a confidence level [10]. This method follows the principles of conformal prediction for regression and uses the intervals of predicted points as an indicator of when anomaly data is appearing. When new data appears out of the upper and lower bounds given by the ICP regressor, by definition, it means that the nonconformist score is higher than the one defined in the confidence level and, thus, the new data is *abnormal* compared to the main distribution [11].

2 Related Work

After the first introduction of conformal prediction in [8] and its use for classification, this methodology has been developed and updated for new purposes. Authors of [9] introduced, for the first time, a method for distribution-independent online learning and anomaly detection, grounded in the theory of conformal prediction, within the context of sea surveillance, where labels are predicted at con-

confidence level $1 - \epsilon$ assuming that the predicted sample and the *normal* training data belongs to the same iid (independent identically distributed) data. Then, an anomaly (or a rare *normal* data point with a probability less than ϵ) is detected when new predictions are empty or do not match the observed label. Thus, the percentage of expected errors or false alarms can be calibrated fine-tuning ϵ . Same authors use Conformal Anomaly Detection (CAD) in video surveillance trajectories, using the Hausdorff distance as the nonconformity score between trajectories. [12]. This work will be extended and improved in [13], where Inductive Conformal Anomaly Detector (ICAD) was proposed to enhance the computational efficiency based on the concept of Inductive Conformal Prediction (ICP) [14], where the training samples are split into a "proper training set" and a "calibration set" where the nonconformity scores are computed.

The nonconformity measure reflects how different data is from the expected distribution. This measure could be the distance to k-neighbours or the residual in a regression model, for example. In [15], authors propose a modification for the EXPoSE algorithm [16] where the kernel-based expected similarity is used as the nonconformity measure in time series data. [17] Introduced Ensemble Conformal Anomaly Detection (ECAD), a distribution-free, unsupervised method that applies conformal prediction to detect anomalies in spatio-temporal data with missing values. ECAD utilizes ensemble regression models to estimate residual-based anomaly scores, ensuring approximate Type-I error control without requiring data exchangeability. It fits ensemble predictors using a regression model and then outputs p-values via locally ranking the test residuals against "leave-one-out" (LOO) training residuals.

This study evaluates neural networks and symbolic regression within the CAD framework. We highlight the flexibility of conformal prediction by integrating symbolic regression, which produces mathematically interpretable formulas, into the normalized conformal predictor method. Residuals serve as the nonconformity score, while points falling outside the confidence interval indicate anomalous data. Symbolic regression, a technique rooted in genetic programming, discovers mathematical expressions that model the relationship between input features and their corresponding outputs. It has been widely applied in fields such as material science [18] to uncover natural laws and medicine [19] for predictive modeling.

3 Data

This study is focused on streaming fault detection using NICP regression in satellite reaction wheel friction data provided by Thales Alenia Space (TAS) ¹, which simulated both nominal and faulty behaviors using their in-house software based on Matlab/Simulink. The anomalies were categorized into four types: 'increase in dry friction (C1), increase in viscous friction (C2), plus two anomalies (C3) and (C4) that concern friction irregularities such as peaks. Each anomaly type

¹<https://www.thalesgroup.com/en/aerospace>

included severity levels ranging from 1 to 3, resulting in 12 distinct anomaly types. The dataset used to train our detector consists of 507 nominal signals generated from a simulated reaction wheel. Each signal contains 22,608 data points, sampled at a frequency that remains undisclosed for confidentiality reasons. Fig. 1 shows the spin rate and friction of an example signal, which are defined as Spin rate: the rotation velocity used as input feature, and Friction: the frictional torque from the reaction wheel serves as an output in our regression model. This torque encompasses both dry and viscous friction produced by the bearings within the reaction wheels. As depicted in Fig. 1 (bottom), the friction profile exhibits several step trends. Ignoring these step trends and considering only the spin rate can lead to underperformance in our methodology, as further discussed in Section 5.

Fig. 1. Spin rate (top) and friction (bottom) in arbitrary units (a.u.) as a function of sample index in a *normal* signal.

4 Methods

This section outlines our anomaly detection methodology and the techniques employed within the conformal prediction framework, beginning with conformal prediction for regression, followed by normalized conformal prediction and symbolic regression.

Fig. 2. NICEP method for anomaly detection.

Fig. 2 illustrates the procedure followed to train and evaluate our NICP-based anomaly detector. The data is first divided into nominal (*normal*) and *abnormal* subsets. The nominal data is then used to train a base regression model. Feature scaling—removing the mean and scaling to unit variance—is also performed using the same training set to ensure consistency in preprocessing. The calibration set is used to train the normalization model, along with the calibration errors computed by the regression model. In our case, we are using the python library *nonconformist* developed by Henrik Linusson [20], where the normalization model estimates the accuracy as described in Eq. 1.

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\log |\hat{y}_i - y_i|} \quad (1)$$

Once our base regression models and normalization models are trained, the normalized nonconformity scores are calculated, and based on these scores, test samples can be predicted. Here, each test sample $x_{t+1} \in X_t$ is composed of 1030 points, as a result of a smoothing procedure to reduce the original 22608 points signal to a more efficient low memory signal. Now, the NICP model is able to predict the confidence intervals for the friction of the reaction wheels as a function of the spin rate given a $(1 - \delta) \cdot 100\%$ confidence. For the regression base models, three different approaches were made:

- **Multi Layer Perceptron (MLP)**: a neural network trained over a 50 points sliding window through the spin rate to predict the next friction point, i.e., $\gamma_{t+1} = f(\omega_{[t-50,t]})$, where $\omega_t \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\gamma_t \in \mathbb{R}$.
- **Spin&Friction_MLP** : same modeling approach as MLP, but considering past observations of friction as additional input variables, to assess their impact on the model quality. This approach also entails including a mechanism to detect and consider the step trends in the friction profile discussed in Section 3. This method uses both the spin rate and a derived feature: the difference in friction between time steps $t + 3$ and t . The inclusion of delta friction is intended to encode step trend information while avoiding data leakage from the output variable into the input, thereby reducing the risk of overfitting.
- **Symbolic Regression**: which estimates the mathematical expression that relates friction to rotational speed, i.e., $\gamma = f(\omega)$.

The MLP models were used to capture temporal features of spin rates and spin friction that are valuable for anomaly detection, while the symbolic regressor focuses on elucidating the relationship between spin rate and friction, offering mathematical explainability alongside predictive capability.

Lastly, models are used in a streaming fashion, where for each reading a confidence interval is estimated and a prediction is obtained. After the real ground truth point of data is received, its belonging to the confidence interval is computed (considering the prediction and interval boundaries). If the real point of

Fig. 3. F1-Score obtained for each anomaly type (1 to 12) for the MLP (green circle), Symbolic Regressor (red cross) or Spin&Friction_MLP (blue triangles) models. Peak adaptation is indicated by stars, specifically for anomalies 6, 7, and 8.

data is outside of the interval, a potential *anomaly point* is detected. If the percentage of *anomaly points* out of the interval in the sliding evaluation window (within said window length w) is higher than $((\delta + \beta) \cdot 100)\%$, an alarm is raised, where β is used as a calibration parameter to optimize the anomaly detection. Subsequently, a threshold is set for each anomaly type that defines when a signal is anomalous based on the number of raised alarms.

To mitigate underperformance in detecting outlier-type anomalies (particularly those related to peak amplitudes) an additional model-specific method is applied. This method refocuses the evaluation window to concentrate on signal peaks, disregarding points that are unrelated to the anomalous behavior.

5 Results

Fig. 3 illustrates the F1-Score obtained for each anomaly type and model. The results indicate comparable performance between the MLP and Symbolic Regressor, suggesting a lack of strong temporal dependency in the friction–spin rate relationship. However, when step trend information is included via the delta friction feature, the model demonstrates a general improved performance. This suggests that, when appropriately encoded, temporality can effectively capture friction step trends, thereby enhancing anomaly detection accuracy. Notably, in anomaly type 4 (which corresponds to a low severity level within the C2 anomaly class), the model underperformed relative to the other methods. Nevertheless, overall, this method can be considered superior in terms of performance.

Symbolic Regressor model represented friction $\gamma(\omega)$ by the equation

$$\gamma(\omega) = \cos(a\omega) + \cos(\omega + b) + \cos(c\omega) + d - \omega,$$

where the parameters a , b , c , and d are determined from proprietary data. This formulation preserves the structure of the original expression while maintaining the confidentiality of the specific numerical values. A performance downgrade was observed in anomalies 6, 7, and 8 during anomaly detection. This can be attributed to the nature of these anomalies, which belong to the C3 category, characterized by variations in peak amplitudes. The NICP algorithm detects anomalies by identifying points that fall outside the predicted interval. Consequently, if an anomaly is localized within specific peaks in the signal rather than affecting its overall behavior, our original approach tends to underperform. The star markers in Fig. 3 (that make reference to previous models evaluated on peaks and defined as MLP_peaks, SymbolicRegressor_peaks and Spin&Friction_MLP_peaks) highlight instances where the sliding window primarily captures friction peaks, rather than other parts of the signal that are less relevant to the anomaly’s nature. Therefore, a notable improvement is observed in anomalies 8 and 9 compared to the original approach, suggesting enhanced detection performance in these cases. Fig. 4 shows an example of an *abnormal* signal (type 9). The MLP model follows the friction profile smoothly but loses performance when step trends occur. In contrast, the Spin&Friction_MLP model produces a noisier prediction but incorporates step trend information, leading to improved anomaly detection. In both signals, the first three peak regions are zoomed in as examples to emphasize that the evaluation specifically targeted these critical segments.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, NICP regression was employed as a tool to model *normal* data within intervals defined by a specified confidence level. This approach enabled the detection of *abnormal* data distributions in satellite reaction wheels. The relationship between spin rate and friction was found to be time-independent for anomaly detection. However, the inclusion of step trend information through delta friction improved the results. The Symbolic Regressor was successfully applied within the CAD framework, and the flexibility of NICP for regression was explored. The resulting formula offers potential for interpretability and explainability of the RAW behavior. Additionally, peak anomalies were improved by refining the original method and focusing the evaluation sliding window on friction peaks. Evaluation was conducted by optimizing both the number of alarms and the window size, which serves as an indicator of how quickly our method can detect anomalies. To further complement this work, more features should be considered other than the spin rate to reduce the mean width intervals in the prediction and increase the NICP regressor performance. Optimizing and searching better configurations for the anomaly detection such as the significance δ could significantly improve the detection results. Also a better threshold selection could improve the anomaly detection, establishing different thresholds or counting the alarm rate per time to define the reaction wheel yield and early detect possible fails in the mechanism.

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Fig. 4. Friction profiles, real (orange), predicted (green) and predicted intervals (blue area) as a function of sample index in an *abnormal* type 9 signal. MLP (top) and Spin&Friction_MLP (bottom) models are shown, with peaks zoomed to illustrate the MLP_peaks and Spin&Friction_MLP_peaks method. Model performance is shown in Figure 3.

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